

2025 in Brief

In 2025, the [Climate Sensitive Infectious Disease Network](#) (CSIDNet) consolidated the foundations built in its first year while continuing to grow a globally distributed, community-led network. We kicked off the Fellowship Program and selected our inaugural cohort, held a community-wide vote through which we selected the Working Groups that will guide 2026 activities, and hosted the 2025 Annual General Meeting (AGM) in Thailand alongside a well-attended parallel virtual component.

This was a year of significant organizational and governance development. We launched our public website, hired two new staff positions, and drafted a communications strategy. We established an interim membership body that participated in two major decision-making processes: a network-wide vote to select Working Groups followed by our first Participatory Budgeting cycle, and elections for the 2026–2027 Governance and Advisory Committees. With high participation, over 70 self-nominations for committee service, and many returning volunteers, these processes demonstrated increasing ownership and excitement about the value of the network and its model of distributed leadership.

Geographic Distribution of Interim Members (75 people)

Key Achievements in 2025

Fellows Selected and Onboarded

After receiving 209 applications from 49 countries in late 2024, in April 2025, CSIDNet [announced its five fellows](#) located in French Polynesia, Ethiopia, Thailand, Argentina, and South Africa. Fellows have been paired with mentors from the Collaborative Committee and attended training on non-violent communication and governance.

Annual General Meeting (AGM): Thailand & Virtual

The [2025 AGM](#) in Thailand brought together members across regions to strengthen relationships, share updates, and align on the Network's direction. A parallel Virtual AGM that included an interactive expo ensured global participation and sustained momentum among members unable to attend in person. Together these two gatherings brought in 100+ participants from more than 40 countries.

member-ownership | mutual aid ethos | sustainable collaborations

Strengthening Community-Led Governance

2025 was a major year for expanding and testing the Network's governance structures. Following the first Annual General Meeting, an interim membership body was established with a closed invitation to the most active community members to join. Approximately 75 members signed an interim membership agreement. Interim members

participated in a network-wide vote to determine the 2026 Working Groups; and elections for the 2026–2027 Governance and Advisory Committees (see open call for [more details](#)). 71 self-nominations were received to fill 8 volunteer committees and the high return rate of volunteers signals growing trust and ownership in the Network's distributed leadership model. Alongside these governance moments, the community itself continued to grow. The CSIDNet listserv now includes over 560 members.

Working Group Selection and Participatory Resource Allocation

In August 2025, interim members voted to endorse Working Groups for the 2026 cycle (see details in the [open call](#)). This was followed by CSIDNet's first Participatory Budgeting process, where Working Group representatives met over 6 facilitated sessions to collectively allocate the available pooled fund of 50,000 USD. Through this process, five Working Groups were selected and resourced to begin their activities in 2026 on topics ranging from community engagement and ethics for CSIDs to co-creating a collaborative repository for cataloging key CSID resources. Participants in these processes gained practical experience building confidence in navigating disagreement, reaching consensus, and stewarding shared resources collectively.

Growing Regional Visibility & Engagement

Throughout 2025, CSIDNet was represented at key convenings across Africa, Asia, and Europe including the Advance Warning and Response Exemplars ([AWARE](#)) [workshop](#) (Nairobi, Kenya), DS-I Africa Exchange (virtual), [Keystone Symposium](#) on Climate Change and Infectious Disease Threats (Hannover, Germany), "[Data and Analytical Tools to Address Research Gaps in Mosquito-Borne Infectious Diseases](#)" (Dar es Salaam, Tanzania); the [Pan-African Conference on Environment,](#)

[Climate Change & Health](#) (Nairobi), the inception meeting of the Modeling of Disease and Health in Africa (MODHA) Network (Nairobi), the Standards for Official Statistics on Climate-Health Interactions (SOSCHI) conference (Kigali, Rwanda); [Reflecting on the Future of Global Community Building](#) (Berlin, Germany); and the WHO Emergency Hub inception meeting of “Strengthening One Health Disease Surveillance and Response In Southern Africa” (virtual). These engagements expanded the Network’s visibility and surfaced new partnership opportunities.

Emerging Impacts

Deepening Sense of Ownership and Belonging: Members reported a growing sense of connection to the Network, strengthened through the annual meeting, committee service, and the Working Group selection and Participatory Budgeting processes. Many described feeling “energized” by being part of a space where contributions are seen and valued, and where leadership is shared rather than centralized.

Strengthened Leadership Across Committees: The high rate of returning volunteers and the 71 self-nominations for committee roles point to increasing member confidence in taking on responsibility and shaping the Network’s direction. Committee members also demonstrated stronger facilitation, coordination, and decision-making skills through year-long activities and two major governance processes.

Growth of Cross-Regional Relationships: The 2025 Thailand + Virtual AGM contributed to new relationships across Africa, Asia, Latin America, and Europe. These relationships are becoming the connective tissue of the Network, supporting future collaboration and peer learning.

Advancing Global Majority–Rooted Governance: Members consistently highlighted that CSIDNet’s governance and culture feel distinctly grounded in Global Majority perspectives and values. The Participatory Budgeting process, consensus-oriented facilitation, and community decision-making were experienced as both unfamiliar and liberating compared to conventional research or institutional environments. This is shaping new expectations about how scientific communities can operate.

Practicing New Forms of Collective Decision-Making: Through the Participatory Budgeting cycle, members practiced co-operative budgeting, voiced concerns, negotiated trade-offs, and reached consensus (through diverse ways beyond “majority rules” voting). Participants described this as a meaningful opportunity to “practice democracy” and learn how to work through differences in ways that strengthened trust and collaboration.

This early feedback suggests that our emphasis on building relationships, shared infrastructure, and leadership pipelines is moving us closer towards realizing a global community of practice rooted in equity, openness, and collaboration that can access, adapt, and mobilize data and modeling tools to effectively respond to CSIDs.

Looking Ahead

In 2026, CSIDNet will focus on strengthening outreach, shared infrastructure, and programming for a growing, globally distributed community. Based on this year's reflections and emerging patterns, our priorities include:

- Launch the Network's membership framework in early 2026 and create more structured pathways for participation and leadership.
- Improve our member communications platform, directory, and a repository to strengthen visibility, documentation, and continuity as the community grows.
- Support Working Groups, Fellows, and more community-led programming on CSID-relevant topics.
- Ensure financial sustainability beyond 2026, including diversified income streams, new partnerships, and stronger evidence of impact.

Highlights

- 560+ members now subscribed to the CSIDNet community listserv.
- 71 self-nominations received for the 2026–2027 Committees.
- 209 fellowship applications from 49 countries, resulting in 5 fellows selected across 4 continents.
- 6 facilitated Participatory Budgeting sessions completed to allocate USD 50,000 across 5 Working Groups for 2026.
- Annual General Meeting delivered (Thailand + Virtual) with 100+ participants
- CSIDNet represented at 6+ regional and global events, including Nairobi, Dar es Salaam, Hannover, and Kigali.
- 8 volunteer committees established supporting ongoing community governance and coordination.

